

Oxidation of Lactic Acid by Acid Dichromate in Presence of $MnSO_4$

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According as a mole of lactic acid takes one, two, or five atoms of oxygen, it may theoretically be oxidised to pyruvic, acetic, or formic acid. The actual oxidation by acid dichromate is slow at room temperature, but quite practicable when sulphuric acid concentration is high and manganous sulphate is present. By suitable choice of conditions pure pyruvic or acetic acid may be formed. There is no evidence of oxidation beyond the acetic acid stage.

The successive oxidation products of lactic acid should be pyruvic, acetic, and formic acids and finally CO_2 . Brown¹ has reported that all these stages are possible at high temperature when the oxidising agent is periodic acid. On the other hand, at ordinary temperatures, acid permanganate oxidises lactic acid to pyruvic and acetic acids only.

The oxidation with acid dichromate is very slow at room temperature as is also the case with oxalic or citric acid. Chatterjee and Gyani² have shown that if *excess* manganous sulphate is present in high sulphuric acid concentrations, oxalic acid may be smoothly oxidised by dichromate, but the reaction with citric acid is still slow. We were naturally interested in ascertaining to what extent manganous sulphate could help in the present oxidation and what pure products could be formed.

EXPERIMENTAL

The oxidations were studied potentiometrically, as described earlier³. It was soon realised that the titration could be performed successfully only with dichromate mixture in the cell. The following stock solutions were maintained: (1) $M/1$ lactic acid, (2) $N/2$ dichromate, (3) $N/2$ manganous sulphate. The last two were suitably diluted when necessary. Measured volumes of pure sulphuric acid were used for bringing the mixture to the required acid concentration. These titrations were always started with 50 ml of $0.005M$ dichromate in the cell. For $MnSO_4$ concentrations above $0.15M$, the required quantity of solid salt was weighed and added to the mixture.

The initial colour of the mixture was found dependent on the concentration of $MnSO_4$ present in the beginning. For low concentrations, it was light orange which deepened and ultimately became cherry-red at high concentrations. The colour gradually

1. *Chem. Abs.*, 1937, 31, 4955.

2. *This Journal*, 1959, 36, 605.

3. *Ibid.*, 1955, 32, 313.

faded as lactic acid was added and was bluish green at the inflection point. A platinum foil electrode ($1 \times 1 \text{ cm}^2$) was used as the indicator electrode and was glowing in a methanol flame before every titration. Normal lactic acid in small amounts was added from a burette at suitable intervals and the E.M.F. measured against a saturated calomel electrode.

Even the initial E.M.F. (before addition of lactic acid) developed slowly. This indicates that in spite of all the care taken, there may have been traces of oxidisable impurities. In more concentrated sulphuric acid solutions, a state of equilibrium was attained in about an hour, but a period of 2 to 3 hours was required when the acid concentration was only 6-10 *N*. Similar difficulties were encountered after each addition of lactic acid. Some relevant figures are recorded in Table II.

TABLE I

Oxidation of lactic acid by acid dichromate in presence of manganese sulphate.

MnSO ₄ .	M/l Lactic acid reqd.	Temp.	MnSO ₄ .	M/l Lactic acid reqd.	Temp.	MnSO ₄ .	M/l Lactic acid reqd.	Temp.
H ₂ SO ₄ conc.=14 <i>N</i> .			H ₂ SO ₄ conc.=12 <i>N</i> .			H ₂ SO ₄ conc.=10 <i>N</i> .		
0.300 <i>M</i>	0.750ml	27°	0.300 <i>M</i>	0.75ml	19°	0.300 <i>M</i>	0.75ml	20.5°
0.050	0.745	20°	0.050	0.75	20°	0.50	0.75	21.5
0.045	0.750	20°	0.045	0.75	20.5°	0.015	0.75	26°
0.040	0.650	19.5°	0.040	0.65	20°	0.010	0.65	22°
0.035	0.625	21°	0.015	0.45	19.8°	0.001	0.55	26°
H ₂ SO ₄ conc.=6 <i>N</i> .			H ₂ SO ₄ conc.=8 <i>N</i> .			H ₂ SO ₄ conc.=6 <i>N</i> .		
0.030	0.550	19°	0.010	0.45	26.5°	0.300	0.75	20°
0.025	0.525	20°	0.005	0.45	21°	0.010	0.75	21°
0.020	0.375	18.5°	0.0025	0.375	26°	0.001	0.75	26°
H ₂ SO ₄ conc.=8 <i>N</i> .			H ₂ SO ₄ conc.=8 <i>N</i> .			H ₂ SO ₄ conc.=8 <i>N</i> .		
0.015	0.375	19.4°	0.001	0.375	26°	0.30	0.75	21°
0.005	0.375	20°				0.010	0.75	21°
0.0025	0.375	19°				0.001	0.75	26°

TABLE II

Time required for equilibrium.

Conc. of H ₂ SO ₄ .	Time for initial-stabilisation.	Time for subsequent additions.	Time req. at inflection point.	Time for initial stabilisation.	Time for subsequent addition.	Time req. at inflection point.
Conc. of MnSO ₄ =0.02 <i>M</i> and below.			Conc. of MnSO ₄ =0.3 <i>M</i> .			
14 <i>N</i>	40-45mins.	10-20mins.	90-120mins.	60 mins.	40-50 mins.	120-150 mins.
12	50-60	20-30	90-120	100	50-60	120-150
10	60-100	30-40	120-150	150	75-100	120-150
8	120-150	40-50	120-150	200	90-120	120-150
6	120-150	60-60	120-150	200	90-120	200

Some of the results of these titrations are shown graphically Figs. 1 and 2. It will be noted that there is one steep inflection in all the graphs. Those in Fig. 1 correspond to the formation of either pure pyruvic acid or pure acetic acid (*vide infra*). Those in Fig. 2 correspond to the formation of a mixture of the two acids. In most cases, where pyruvic acid is formed, there is a vague initial inflection. This could not be due to the formation of acetic acid since this cannot be subsequently reduced to pyruvic.

FIG. 1

Since we started with 50 ml of 0.005M dichromate in all these titrations, the mixture will provide two atoms of oxygen per molecule of lactic acid at 0.375 ml of *N/1* acid added and the product will be acetic acid

at 2×0.375 ml or 0.750 ml of acid added; only one atom of oxygen per molecule is consumed and the product should be pyruvic acid:

Production of formic acid will require 5 atoms oxygen (0.15 ml acid) and the complete oxidation to CO_2 and water will require 6 atoms (0.125ml acid). The last two stages have not been realised in these experiments. The complete data are recorded in Table I.

FIG. 2

DISCUSSION

It will be noted from Table I that a high concentration of H_2SO_4 (12-14*N*) and a low concentration of manganous sulphate (0.025*M* or less in 14*N*- H_2SO_4 and 0.0025*M* or less in 12*N*) are necessary in order to oxidise lactic acid to acetic acid completely. The concentration of the salt must not fall below 0.045*M* in 12-14*N*- H_2SO_4 and 0.015*M* in 10*N*, if pure pyruvic acid has to be formed. In 6-8*N*- H_2SO_4 , the concentration of MnSO_4 may be anything and the only product is pyruvic acid.

The following equations show that under standard conditions, the dichromate ion is unable to oxidise Mn^{2+} to the manganic state:

Under the conditions of our experiments, the development of red colour on mixing dichromate and manganous sulphate shows, however, that manganic ions are formed. This is also supported by Chakravarty and Ghosh⁴. The values of the two E_0 's must be altered by the presence of H_2SO_4 . In the case of the first electrode it is obvious. Perhaps complex formation with sulphate or bisulphate ions may account for the change in the value of the second E_0 . The net result is that E.M.F. of the cell, as written in reaction (iii), becomes positive and manganic ions are produced. The question arises why the dichromate cannot oxidise lactic acid directly if the reduction potential of Mn^{3+} (reverse of ii) is smaller than that in reaction (i), modified by conditions of our experiments. Obviously, activation energies seem to be involved and the oxidation by manganic ions perhaps requires a smaller one.

The rates definitely improved in more concentrated acid solutions. This clearly indicates that hydrogen ions are not only required for reduction of dichromate (reaction i), but act as catalysts in the actual oxidation of the organic acids. Oxidation to pyruvic acid is easy to picture. A hydrogen ion may attach itself to the carbon carrying the OH, forming an unstable intermediate. The two hydrogen atoms on this carbon may then split off as a water molecule on the approach of oxygen atom. Finally the hydrogen on the hydroxyl may split off as a proton, leaving a neutral molecule of pyruvic acid.

It will be further noted that the direction in which we have performed these titrations may be more convenient experimentally but less instructive. From the above discussions it appears convincing that what we are following in the graphs of Figs. 1 and 2 are not oxidation of lactic acid but reduction of Mn^{3+} to Mn^{2+} . The initial indefinite inflections in some graphs (in which pyruvic acid is formed) merely indicate that the Mn^{3+} may be passing through a state of oxidation between Mn^{3+} and Mn^{2+} . A titration performed with dichromate in the burette may be more instructive if it could be made experimentally satisfactory. It would show the various oxidation stages through which lactic acid may pass. This matter is receiving our further attention.

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